

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

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STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Meng, J., & Lou, W. (2022). Assessment and prediction of the quality of scientific reviews: A text mining method. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti2246). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6907096>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

Assessment and prediction of the quality of scientific reviews: A text mining method

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Introduction

Peer review lies at the foundation of scientific evaluation. However, the effectiveness of peer-review is being continuously questioned. A hot issue of the peer-review process is the reproducibility of review outcomes. The subjectivity, including randomness and bias is at the heart of the irreproducibility of the review process. The well-known NIPS experiment [1] yielded the observation that 43% of papers accepted to the conference would be accepted again if the conference review process were repeated. Apart from that, peer review has been challenged by the rapid increase of paper submissions recently. For example, at International Conference of Representations (ICLR), the number of submissions has grown by an order of magnitude within the last 5 years alone. There is an influx of researchers from disparate fields and different expertise levels into the field due to the shortage of qualified professional reviewers, and the submitted reviews do not always meet the conformity standards of the conferences or journals [4]. All of these issues call into question the effectiveness of the review process. To assess the review process and improve its effectiveness, we examine two concrete research questions,

Q1: How can we evaluate the review quality?

First, we quantify what constitutes a good review. We evaluate review quality from multiple perspectives, in which we claim a good review not only should make a good recommendation, but also should meet the conformity standards of publishers. Three metrics *Racc*, *Pai*, and *Rcon*, are proposed to evaluate reviews in terms of recommendation accuracy, predictive accuracy of impact, and review conformity respectively. Furthermore, we assess the review process utilizing these metrics. We found that these indicators became worse over time.

Q2: What are the effective features to distinguish the quality of the reviews?

An essential task in the review process comes at the end when the meta-reviewers have to make a decision as to accept a paper or not combing the opinions of several reviewers and papers. However, the submitted reviews do not always meet the standards of the conferences. The randomness of the review scores can also mislead the meta-reviewer. Such a situation poses an ever-bigger burden on the meta-reviewers. To tackle the problem, we develop a feature-rich

prediction model to predict the quality of the review, which not only assists the meta-reviewer in making decisions; but also helps to identify the effective features of low-quality reviews.

Dataset

OpenReview¹ was a primary source of data, which provides open access to reviews and evaluation scores for all submissions of ICLR. Besides, multiple sources to enable an analysis of many factors are also scraped.

Reviews. We have crawled 5,575 submissions and 17,028 official reviews from ICLR 2017-2020 venues on the OpenReview. We use the review data since 2017 because the data before 2017 is very noisy and incomplete. For each submission, we include the following metadata information that we can obtain from the review web page: abstract text, review text, meta-review text, and decisions.

Citations. Citation counts were obtained from SemanticScholar² for all the papers from 2017 to 2019. When encountering any ambiguity paper titles, we screened for duplicate publications using a Levenshtein edit distance metric.

Conformity scores. To evaluate the review conformity (see next section), we need to grade these reviews. Ines Arous et. al have conducted a large-scale crowdsourcing study for review grading, in which they asked participants to provide ratings for each of the eight conformity criteria for each of the reviews [2]. However, the data is not enough due to the heavy load. We further selected some reviews for grading, mainly from 2017 and 2019, based on the eight criteria.

Multi-perspective Evaluation

Metrics

Recommendation accuracy (Racc)

One of the main purposes of the review is to whether the article is qualified for the journal. A good review should take a clear stance, selecting high-quality submissions for publication.[3] We define Recommendation Accuracy (*Racc*) to measure whether the stance of the review *R* is consistent with the actual accept/reject decision of the reviewed paper. *Racc* is calculated as

$$Racc(R) = Dec(D) \times Rec(R) + 1$$

where $Rec(R) \in \{-1,0,1\}$ indicates the recommendation degree of a review, with $\{-1, 0, 1\}$ representing negative, neutral and positive. $Dec(D) \in \{-1,1\}$ represents the final decision of a submission by the meta-review: "accept" or "reject". [details ...]. To facilitate machine learning and analysis, we map the range of *Racc* to $\{0,1,2\}$ by adding one. A higher score indicates that the review more decisively and accurately makes an acceptance recommendation.

Predictive accuracy of impact (Pai)

A review process can still be quite bad if it rejects high-impact and transformative papers. A good review should give a good estimate of the importance and potential impact of the article. Here we measure impact using citation rate, calculated by dividing citation count by the number of days since the paper was first published online. We define Predictive accuracy of impact (*Pai*) to represent the extent to which the review predicts the impact and importance of a submission:

$$Pai = 2 - |Cita(S) - Rec(R)|$$

¹ <https://openreview.net/>

² <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>

Here, the citation rate of submission, $Cita(S)$ is discretized into $\{-1,0,1\}$ by the following method: The citation rate follows a power-law distribution, $CITA \sim x^a$, so we have $\log CITA \sim a \log x$. The straight line $a \log x$ is then equidistantly divided into three intervals, each corresponding to $\{-1,0,1\}$. To be consistent with the range of $Racc$, we subtract the distance between $Cita(S)$ and the recommended score $Rec(R)$ by 2. Hence, $Pai \in \{0,1,2\}$. The higher the Pai , the more accurate the prediction of impact.

Review Conformity (Rcon)

The submitted reviews should meet the conformity standards of the conferences such as the presence of sufficient justification for the claims. The criteria for review conformity can be found in review guidelines published by journals, conferences [5,7], publishers [8], and the literature [2,3]. Here we group those criteria into the following three categories.

- a. *Comprehensiveness*: Consistency: there should be no contradiction between the contexts, as well as the recommended score and the arguments.[8] Clarity: A review should be well-organized, containing a summary of the paper, supporting arguments and the decision.
- b. *Justifications*: A review should provide specific reasons for its assessment, by including hints about how the authors could improve problematic aspects and some references. [3]
- c. *Objectivity*: It includes two parts. 1) Fairness: A review should not be biased towards irrelevant factors such as assigning a low score because of missing references from the reviewer's work only. 2) Offensiveness: A review should cover the technical work rather than giving personal statements and/or offensive terms.[2]

It is difficult to quantify $Rcon$, so we take a human+ML approach to grade review conformity. Ines Arous et. al subdivided the above three categories into eight criteria. Based on these criteria, they have graded part of the reviews by conducting a crowdsourcing study. Even if we have also extended the labeled reviews, they still account for only a small percentage. Therefore, we further graded the remaining reviews' conformity levels by machine learning method. Details can be found in the next section.

Metrics Evaluations

We can evaluate the effectiveness of the review process utilizing the defined metrics. We study how these key metrics evolved and their connections.

1. Distribution

The distribution of three metrics is shown in Fig 1. We use low, medium, and high to denote the $Racc/Pai$ scores 0,1,2 respectively. We find that the percentage of low-quality reviews is low for all three metrics (7% for $Racc$; 10% for Pai). $Rcon$ follows a normal distribution with mean 2.72 and variance 1.23.

2. The variation of the metrics over time

The percentage of each score for Pai and $Racc$ is illustrated in Fig 3. Table 1 presents the average values for each indicator. We make several observations. First, with the number of submissions increased, the mean of $Racc$ and $Rcon$ went down significantly each year. They fell by 19% and 15% respectively from 2017 to 2019; It can be seen from Fig. 3 that the percentage of high- $Racc$ also declined year by year. The results indicate that recommendation accuracy and the review conformity became worse over time. Second, the average of Pai changed slightly, but the proportion of high- Pai is on the decline. Third, for both Pai and $Racc$, the proportion of medium grew significantly, indicating that reviewers are becoming more conservative in their recommendations.

Table 1. The average values for three metrics

Year	# submissions	RACC	PAI	RCON
2017	1486	0.966	1.36	2.981
2018	2748	0.843	1.37	2.752
2019	4329	0.741	1.30	2.715

3. Correlation Analysis

The strength of the nonlinear relationship between the indicators is measured by Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient. We also calculated the correlation coefficient between the metrics and confidence scores (*conf*), as well as the review rating (*rating*). The result is shown in Fig. 2.

Among the three pairs of indicators, Pai has the highest correlation with *Racc* (0.28, $p < 0.001$), which we believe because they are both associated with *Rec*. The Spearman correlation (0.16, $p < 0.001$) reflects a moderate relationship between *Rcon* and *Racc*. It is worth noting that there is always a weak positive correlation between *conf* and all three indicators, which we will continue to investigate in the next section.

Fig. 1. The distributions of the three metrics

Fig. 2. The correlation matrix

Fig. 3. The proportions of different scores from 2017 to 2019

Review Quality Prediction

In the previous section, we found that the general quality of reviews declined as the submission increased. As a result, a question arises as to how to detect low-quality reviews, and what are the effective features to detect them. In this section, we propose and study the review quality prediction task for three reasons: 1. Investigating impact Features on distinguishing review quality. 2. Only a small proportion of the review text was graded, so we hope to learn the *Rcon* values of the remaining reviews through machine learning methods for further analysis 3. Assisting the meta-reviewer to screen reviews and make a decision.

Prediction Model

Let I be the set of reviews, our goal is to infer the three scores $\{Racc, Pai, Rcon\}$ for all reviews $i \in I$ using

$$f(r_i, a_i^p) \rightarrow \{Racc, Pai, Rcon\}$$

where r_i, a_i^p represents review feature vectors and the abstract text belonging to paper p and review i . The task can be regarded as three subtasks of predicting *Racc*, *Pai*, *Hrt*, which are denoted as t_r, t_p, t_c respectively. The three subtasks can be modeled as a multi-classification problem or a regression problem. In this paper, we choose three machine learning algorithms, which are common models used in text mining tasks, including Support Vector Machine/Regression (SVM/SVR) as a kernel machine, Random Forest Classifier/Regressor (RFC/RFR) as an ensemble of trees, and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) as a gradient boosting algorithm. These models have low computational requirements and empirically demonstrated good classification accuracy.

Feature Engineering

Score features: We use all peer review scores (*rev_score*) and confidence scores (*conf_score*) for a given submission to build an array of score-based features. These include their difference with the scores of the other reviews on the same paper and statistics of all peer reviews.

Linguistic features: In this study, we introduce four linguistic features to measure the characteristics of the content of the review: Length of review (*rev_len*), we use the logarithm of the number of tokens in reviews as a feature. Readability (*read*): The Dale-Chall readability formula is used to calculate it. Review-Abstract Similarity (*sim_ab*). The first step of a review is summarizing the paper's contribution. A Lack of similarity between an abstract and its review may indicate that the response is "off-topic". Therefore, the similarity can be used to measure the review quality.

Sentiment features: Sentiment analysis centers on identifying the viewpoint underlying the documents. We propose to implement the sentiment features in our tasks with sentiment analysis techniques, including sentiment polarity (*pol*) and subjectivity (*sub*).

Table 2. Summary of the proposed feature set.

Category	Abbreviation	Feature
Score features	<i>rev_score</i>	review scores
	<i>conf_score</i>	confidence scores
Linguistic features	<i>rev_len</i>	review length
	<i>read</i>	readability
	<i>sim_ab</i>	similarity with abstract
Sentiment features	<i>pol</i>	sentiment polarity
	<i>sub</i>	subjectivity

Prediction Result

To evaluate the performance of different methods on our tasks, we adopt two evaluation metrics for classification tasks, including accuracy (*ACC*), F1 score(weighted) (*F1*); We choose MAE, RMSE to evaluate the performance of regression task. MAE and RMSE measure the difference between the real value and the predicted value for a regression task.

Prediction results obtained with each subtask are presented in Table 3. Among the three models the Random Forest model achieves the best performance on all three tasks. This might be because it is robust to oversampling biases in highly imbalanced datasets. RF based on all features had a F1-score more than 0.6 and MSE-score less than 0.12. This indicated that they made a more accurate prediction. Compared with the SVM model and MLP model, RF model has lower time and space consumption. Therefore, RF model is also suitable considering that in actual use where the amount of data will be much larger than the data in the experiment. We use RF predictions for further analysis.

Table 3. Prediction Results

Model	t_r		t_p		t_c	
	Acc	F1	Acc	F1	Acc	F1
SVC(SVR)	0.907	0.8709	0.580	0.548	0.267	0.112
RFC(RFR)	0.921	0.886	0.632	0.620	0.2551	0.107
MLP	0.920	0.831	0.620	0.587	0.583	0.516

Analysis

To interpret our results, we study the importance score of the features in our Random Forest model shown in Table 4. To demonstrate the distinction between reviews with different quality levels, we also present the distribution of the different features for both high-quality reviews and low-quality reviews in Fig. 3. We observe the following trends:

As can be seen from Tab. 4, for task t_r, t_p , the sentiment features such as polarity are considerably more informative compared to other features except for *rev_score*. As shown in Fig. 4(b), through the sentiment analyses, on average, the emotions expressed by the high-*Pai* reviews (0.096) are more neutral than the low-*Pai* (0.122), which is also true for *Racc* (0.10 vs 0.12). Moreover, review length is also effective features for *Racc* and *Pai*. It can be seen from Fig. 4(a) that the high-*Racc* reviews are longer than low-*Racc* on average (463 vs 426), and the case of *Pai* is similar. Besides, as shown in Fig. 3(e-f), we observe that reviews with high

confidence tend to be high-*Racc* and high-*Pai*. In the case of *Racc*, 73.4% of high-*Racc* reviews had a confidence score of 4 or higher, while the percentage is 64.4% in low-*Racc*.

In terms of the *Rcon*, *conf*, *sim_ab*, *rev_len* are more informative features. The cumulative distribution in Fig. 4(c) shows that the high-*Rcon* reviews, with 491 words on average, tend to be longer than the low-*Rcon* that averaged 458 words. In addition, low-*Rcon* reviews have lower confidence scores (3.89 vs 3.76) and lower *sim_ab* scores (0.064 vs 0.045) than the high-*Rcon* reviews. It implies that the low-conformity reviews tend to be less confident and more inconsistent with the abstract of the paper.

In sum, review length, polarity, and confidence score are three important factors that distinguish the quality of a review. Low-quality reviews have shorter lengths, lower confidence, and less neutral sentiment, all of which will help meta-reviewers value more worthy reviews when making final decisions.

Table 4. The importance score of each feature

Feature\Metric	Racc	Pai	Rcon
pol	0.064	0.148	0.054
sub	0.057	0.143	0.026
rev_len	0.059	0.142	0.308
confi	0.017	0.034	0.074
rating	0.680	0.231	0.005
sim_ab	0.058	0.145	0.084
read	0.055	0.139	0.074

a. review length for *Racc*

b. sentiment polarity for *Pai*

c. review length for *Rcon*

d. similarity with abstract for *Rcon*

Fig. 4. The distributions of the low-quality reviews and high-quality reviews for the proposed features

Conclusion

In this paper, we propose three metrics $Racc$, Pai , and $Rcon$ to evaluate review quality. We collect the whole ICLR review corpus for the years 2017-2019 with all metadata. Utilizing the defined metrics, we evaluate the effectiveness of review process from multi-aspects. All three indicators declined as the submission increased. And reviewers are becoming more conservative in their recommendations. In addition, we proposed a model to predict the review quality. The result from Random Forest model shows that the review length, sentiment polarity, and confidence scores are three important factors that distinguish the quality of a review, which will assist meta-reviewers value more worthy reviews.

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